

Chemistry of Vanadium and Molybdenum Complexes— Some Results and Future Prospects*

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The chemistry of the coordination compounds of vanadium and molybdenum is topical due to their involvement in processes of biological importance. Both of them exhibit a number of oxidation states and form a wide variety of mono- and binuclear complexes with ligands containing several donor atoms. Using the multidentate ligands and biologically important imidazole and its derivatives, a large number of complexes have been synthesised and characterised by several techniques including EPR and NMR spectroscopy and electrochemical techniques. These techniques will assume a greater relevance in future providing challenges and opportunities in investigating the chemistry of vanadium and molybdenum and may highlight future prospects.

The transition metal ions vanadium and molybdenum have many striking similarities and both exhibit a number of accessible oxidation states and coordination numbers with a variety of polyhedral structures. Both of them are strikingly similar in forming strong oxo complexes in their high oxidation states where the metal-oxygen bond has a significant double bond character. Both of them are biologically significant and are also of interest from structural, chemical and electrochemical aspects.

Vanadium occurs widely in certain petroleum oils notably those from Venezuela and it can be isolated from them as oxovanadium(IV) porphyrins¹. Other oxovanadium porphyrins have also been synthesised². Vanadium is endogenous to some living systems, e.g. sea squirts, tunicates and at least one mushroom³⁻⁵, although its role is obscure⁶. The accumulation of a given element by a living system is one of the most fascinating phenomenon and one of the metal ions involved in such processes is the oxovanadium(IV) ion which is normally not an essential element. The biological chemistry of vanadium is established for a novel natural product, *amavadin*, in the mushroom *Amanita muscaria*^{4,7,8} which contains the anion of the *N*-hydroxy-2,2'-iminodipropionic acid.

Vanadium is also a potent inhibitor of phosphoryl transfer enzymes⁹, an activity resulting from the formation of a stable pentacoordinate vanadium(V) species generated as an analogue of the phosphorous transition state^{10,11}. Vanadium is involved in phospholipid oxidation, sulphur metabolism and cholesterol biosynthesis¹² and the peroxo-hetero-ligand vanadates represent a model system for studying some biochemical interaction of vanadium in living matter¹³ and there is a relationship between the chemical composition and the biological activity (antitumour activity-toxicity). Several investigations into biologically relevant vanadium compounds have been made¹⁴⁻¹⁶. Recent studies show that peroxovanadium complexes have potent insulin-like activity, suggesting that they could be orally active alternatives to insulin¹⁷.

Molybdenum is a versatile transition metal and a number of chemical reactions are catalysed by complexes of molybdenum. Molybdenum compounds provide the active centres for such processes as dehydrosulphurisation¹⁸ and for oxygen atom transfer reactions such as epoxidation and de-epoxidation^{19,20}. The useful role of molybdenum is not restricted to industrial type catalytic reactions. Nature has incorporated molybdenum into a number of redox enzymes²¹, and thus is an

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essential micronutrient for microorganisms²², plants²³ and animals²⁴. These include among others aldehyde, sulphite and xanthine oxidase, nitrate reductase and nitrogenase. These enzymes catalyse the conversion of molecular nitrogen to ammonia, nitrite to nitrate, sulphite to sulphate, xanthine to uric acid and aldehydes to carboxylic acids respectively. Dioxomolybdenum(IV) complexes with polydentate nitrogen, sulphur and oxygen ligands are considered valuable models for the active sites of several Mo-enzymes²⁵⁻²⁷. The common feature associated with both the industrial and biological reactions is that molybdenum serves as the site for catalytic redox reactions.

Work in our laboratory has been concerned with the coordination chemistry of several transition and inner-transition elements for more than three decades and it is proposed to discuss here contributions from this group in the area of coordination chemistry of vanadium and molybdenum, in their stable oxidation states, employing ligands of biological relevance or importance. These two metal ions are of topical importance and further, the space will not permit discussion of entire contributions from this laboratory in the area of transition metals and one had to make hard choice. The review that follows is not intended to be complete, but it is hoped that it will present some insight into this area of study and activity. Attention has been focussed on oxovanadium(IV) and dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes, as in high oxidation states these oxo-compounds are rather stable and the metal-oxygen multiple bond also provides an additional probe for investigation.

Oxovanadium(IV) complexes

Although vanadium compounds with formal oxidation states from 3- upto 5+ are known, under ordinary conditions, the stable states are 4+ and 5+. The most stable under ordinary conditions is the 4+ oxidation state and the majority of the vanadium(IV) compounds contain the VO^{2+} unit (vanadyl ion), which can persist through a variety of reactions. Its complexes typically have square-pyramidal or square-bipyramidal geometry with the vanadyl oxygen apical and the V atom lying about 0.035–0.055 Å above the plane defined

by the equatorial ligands²⁸, although few trigonal bipyramidal complexes are also known. The VO^{2+} entity bonds most effectively to the more electronegative atoms, e.g. F, Cl, O, N (and also S and P). Although not completely unambiguous, the ordering of molecular orbitals has been discussed on the basis of optical and epr spectra²⁹⁻³³. The epr spectra yield A_0 (isotropic hyperfine splitting constant) and g_0 (isotropic g) values in reasonably well-defined ranges characteristic of the types of metal ligand bonds³⁴, and provide information on the stereochemistry, ligand type and degree of covalency of vanadium(IV) complexes. Also, the $\nu_{V=O}$ band generally observed at $985 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is an im-

portant characteristic of oxovanadium(IV) complexes, and is quite sensitive to the nature of the ligands²⁹. Several oxovanadium(IV) compounds have magnetic moments close to the spin-only value of 1.73 B.M. for one unpaired electron³⁵, although some oxovanadium(IV) complexes show magnetic moments considerably lower than the spin-only value, perhaps due to dimerisation leading to vanadium-vanadium interaction.

Apart from oxovanadium(IV) halides, pseudohalides, sulphate and nitrate, the vanadyl bis(β -diketonato) compounds, $[\text{VO}(\beta\text{-diketonato})_2]$ are good sources for the generation of VO^{2+} ion. Bis(acetylacetonato)oxovanadium(IV), $\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2$ ³⁶ has a square-pyramidal geometry³⁷ and is the prime example of this geometry in coordination compounds³⁸. In this and in similar compounds the V=O bond length is ~157–169 pm, which

is about 50 pm shorter than the four equatorial V–O bonds³⁷. The magnetic moment is in the range 1.71–1.76 B.M.³⁹ and the room temperature epr spectrum of $[\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2]$ in toluene consists of the eight lines expected for a species of spin 7/2 with $g = 1.971$ and an average coupling constant of 120 G⁴⁰. Electrochemistry of $\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2$ in DMSO studied by cyclic voltammetry and controlled-potential coulometry at a platinum electrode shows that it is irreversibly reduced by one electron at -1.9 V vs SCE to a stable vanadium(III) product⁴¹. The one-electron oxidation of $\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2$ at +0.81 V vs SCE gives a vanadium(V) product. Solvent effects and adduct formation of $[\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2]$ and related complexes have been studied by several methods and $\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2$ is shown to add a sixth ligand according to equation (1).

(D = donor solvent or ligand)

This expansion of the coordination number by the formation of adducts is facilitated as the maximum coordination number of vanadium(IV) in $\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2$ is not reached. By employing unidentate donor ligands, complexes of the above type $[\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2(\text{D})]$ can be conveniently synthesised from $\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2$. The most characteristic feature of the ir spectra of these complexes is the appearance of a strong band at 995 cm^{-1} for the $\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2$ complex due to $\nu_{\text{V}=\text{O}}$ ⁴². Donation of electrons from the axial ligands increases the electron density in the vanadium d -orbitals and thus reduces the donation from the vanadyl oxygen reducing the V=O bond character. This results in lowering of $\nu_{\text{V}=\text{O}}$ from 995 cm^{-1} in $\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2$ by about 40–50 to 950–955 cm^{-1} in the $[\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2(\text{D})]$ complexes. Although five-coordinate oxovanadium(IV) compounds resist σ -donation at times⁴³, in case of imidazole complexes they do accept a ligand and enhance the coordination number⁴⁴. Several such six-coordinate complexes have been synthesised using imidazole ligands (Table 1).

TABLE 1— $\nu_{\text{V}=\text{O}}$ BAND AND ROOM TEMPERATURE MAGNETIC MOMENTS OF $[\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2(\text{D})]$ COMPLEXES

Compd ^a	$\nu_{\text{V}=\text{O}}$ cm^{-1}	μ_{eff} B M
$\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2$	995	1.73
$\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2(\text{Im})$	955	1.76
$\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2(1\text{-MeIm})$	954	1.65
$\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2(1\text{-EtIm})$	954	1.68
$\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2(1\text{-AlIm})$	954	1.74
$\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2(1\text{-ViIm})$	952	1.61
$\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2(1\text{-Vi-2-MeIm})$	950	1.80
$\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2(\text{BzIm})$	955	1.82

^aIm = imidazole; Me = methyl, Et = ethyl; Al = allyl; Vi = vinyl; 1-Vi-2-Me = 1-vinyl 2-methyl, BzIm = benzimidazole.

The electronic spectra and magnetic moment measurements are as expected. The observed magnetic moments of these complexes $[\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2(\text{D})]$ (D = imidazole or substituted imidazole) lie in the range 1.6–1.8 B.M., close to the spin-only value of d^1 systems⁴⁵. The thermogravimetric measurements of these complexes reveal their stability. On thermolysis, initially imidazole ligand is lost followed by acac, finally yielding V_2O_5 as the end-product.

Fig. 1. Thermal decomposition curve for $[VO(acac)_2(1-VIm)]$ complex.

We next consider oxovanadium(IV) complexes with bi- and higher-dentate Schiff base ligands and imidazole derivatives. With bidentate Schiff bases, normally monomeric $VO(SB)_2$ complexes are formed similar to $VO(acac)$. However, with tridentate Schiff base ligands, often dimeric species are formed, and compounds with anomalous magnetic moments are obtained⁴⁶. Ginsberg *et al.*⁴⁶ studied the magnetic properties of these compounds in detail in the temperature range 1.4–300 K and found that the moments decreased considerably as the temperature is lowered, a phenomenon characteristic of intramolecular antiferromagnetic exchange. For these dimeric complexes, the exchange integral (J) was determined using the Bleaney-Bowers equation⁴⁷.

On treatment of **5** with a strong chelating agent, such as phenanthroline, the dimer is broken and a mononuclear mixed-ligand complex, $[VO(SB)(phen)]$ ($SB =$ tridentate ONO Schiff base ligand;

$phen =$ phenanthroline), is formed⁴⁸. The dimer is also broken on treatment of complex **5** with pyridine, and a monopyridine adduct $[VO(SB)(py)]$ is formed that obeys the Curie-Weiss law with $\theta = 2K$ and room temperature μ_{eff} of 1.75 B.M.⁴⁹. The dimeric structure for compounds with various ONO tridentate Schiff bases have been formulated as $[VO(SB)_2]$ with structure **6** on the basis of magnetic properties and ir spectra.

The potential tridentate Schiff base anthranilic acid salicylideneimine has ONO donor sites and may coordinate to VO^{2+} in the presence of a unidentate donor ligand (D) such as imidazole or its derivatives to form either five-coordinate complexes, $[VO(SB)(D)]$ or the six-coordinate complexes, $[VO(SB)(D)_2]$. However, the structure was shown to be octahedral and dimeric leading to a lower magnetic moment and thus, preventing the entry of either a donor solvent molecule or an extra imidazole⁵⁰. It is evident that the ONO donor set of the tridentate Schiff base forces the VO^{2+} ion to dimerise leading to antiferromagnetic properties^{51,52}. The coupling of two $S = 1/2$ spins of the VO^{2+} ions leads to a singlet state ($S = 0$) and a thermally accessible triplet state ($S = 1$), separated by the exchange integral. The populations of the molecules in the two spin states then follows the Maxwell-Boltzman distribution law. Thus, the oxygen-bridged structure **8** appears to be a reasonable model.

The epr spectrum of polycrystalline $[VO(SB)(Im)]_2$ ($H_2SB =$ anthranilic acid salicylideneimine **7**; $Im =$ imidazole or substituted imidazole) solids

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at room and liquid helium (4.2 K) temperature at X-band frequencies show a single unresolved epr signal at $g = 1.9715$ ⁵⁰. The eight hyperfine lines due to ^{51}V are not resolved and the line width is about 80 G. The hyperfine interaction of ^{51}V being quite large (~ 100 G)⁵³⁻⁵⁵, small linewidths of epr lines due to VO^{2+} in $[\text{VO}(\text{SB})\text{(Im)}]_2$ may be attributed to rapid electron exchange between the two vanadium nuclei of the dimeric structure 8. For compounds containing substituted imidazole ligands as the axial donors, $[\text{VO}(\text{SB})\text{(D)}]_2$, both broadening and shifting of the epr lines were observed, may be due to the slowing down of the reorientational motion of imidazole derivatives containing bulkier groups like the alkyl or other groups in place of hydrogen. The epr lines also broaden further with decreasing temperature again due to the slowing down of reorientational motion at lower temperature (4.2 K). The variation in g values (Table 2) may be explained on the basis of electron-donating or electron-withdrawing character of the substituents at 1- or 2-position of the imidazole ring which affects the electron density at the ligating site (N-3).

TABLE 2—EPR, MAGNETIC MOMENT AND IR DATA OF $[\text{VO}(\text{SB})(\text{D})]_2$ COMPLEXES

Compd. $[\text{VO}(\text{SB})(\text{D})]_2$	$\nu_{\text{V=O}}$ cm^{-1}	μ_{eff} B.M.	$\langle g \rangle$
D =			
Im	875	1.41	1.972
1-MeIm	880	1.46	2.004
1-EtIm	881	1.47	2.019
1-ViIm	880	1.37	1.970
1-Allm	882	1.40	1.954
2-MeIm	880	1.38	1.994
2-EtIm	880	1.39	2.004
1,2-DiMeIm	880	1.40	1.945

H_2SB = Anthranilic acid salicylideneimine.

Fig. 2. Epr spectra of dimeric $[\text{VO}(\text{SB})(1\text{-EtIm})]_2$ (H_2SB = anthranilic acid salicylideneimine) at room (293 K) and liquid helium (4.3 K) temperatures.

With the bidentate bi-heterocyclic ligand, 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole (PBH)⁵⁶ (9), both five-

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and six-coordinated complexes of oxovanadium(IV) are formed. The complexes $[\text{VO}(\text{PBH})_2](\text{NCS})_2$, $[\text{VO}(\text{PBH})\text{SO}_4]$ and $[\text{VO}(\text{PBH})_2]\text{SO}_4$ are five-coordinated, while $[\text{VO}(\text{PBH})_2\text{X}]\text{X}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{NO}_3$) are six-coordinated⁵⁷. The magnetic moments of these complexes (1.70–1.87 B.M.) do not show any antiferromagnetic coupling and the X-band epr spectra provide g_{av} value in the range 1.983–2.002 close to the free-electron spin-only value of 2.0023⁵⁷. In all cases the epr signal appears as an unresolved broad line except for the

and leaving one or two secondary nitrogens free from coordination in case of the pentadentate H₂DMDT and the hexadentate H₂DMTT ligands, respectively. Similar behaviour has been shown with these ligands for cobalt(II,III)^{60,61}, uranium(VI)⁶², thorium(VI)⁶² and also molybdenum(VI)⁶³, where binuclear complexes with two metal centres bridged by the oxime-based Schiff base ligands were obtained. The ESCA spectra for cobalt(III) complexes support the bridged structure⁶⁴, and it is interesting that the same type of behaviour is seen also for oxovanadium(V) complexes. The electrochemical data in DMSO show reductive waves in the narrow region of -0.16 to -0.28 V corresponding to the reduction from vanadium(V) to vanadium(IV)⁵⁹.

Dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes

Molybdenum is unique among the transition elements of the second and third transition series¹ and exhibits a variety of oxidation states varying from 1- to 6+ and consequently has a wide range of stereochemistries^{21,65} rendering its chemistry one of the most complex among the transition elements. The importance of molybdenum may be appreciated as it is the only element among the heavier transition elements which has a major role as a trace element in enzymes. It is capable of forming both Wernerian as well as non-Wernerian complexes⁶⁶ and plays a significant role in industrial catalytic reactions. The importance and topical relevance of molybdenum is highlighted by realising that it is one of the few elements which has its own series of international conferences⁶⁷. Although molybdenum exhibits a large number of oxidation states, the 6+ state is the most stable and forms a large number of coordination complexes. In the hexavalent state the chemistry is dominated by

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the oxo ligand and its analogues. The oxo ligand, O²⁻, stabilises a large number of formally Mo(6+) complexes, although it is now recognised that the sulphido (S²⁻), selenido (Se²⁻), peroxido (O₂²⁻), persulphido (S₂²⁻), imido (NR²⁻) and the nitrido (N³⁻) as well as the hydrazido (R₂NN²⁻) and hydroxylamido (R₂NO⁻) etc. ions can form complexes that may be regarded as analogues in oxo chemistry. Indeed, the oxo chemistry stands as a guidepost from which one can extrapolate to make predictions of the structural chemistry of its analogue ligands. The tetrahedral molybdate ion is the key antecedent for much molybdenum(VI)

chemistry and this ion serves as the starting point for many of the preparative schemes in the chemistry of molybdenum(vi). Complexes containing the MoO_2^{2+} core are by far the most common in molybdenum(vi) chemistry and these are invariably six-coordinate with near-octahedral geometry containing the *cis*-dioxo groups. In these complexes, the Mo–O_t distances and the O_t–Mo–O_t angles are fairly identical and lie in a narrow range. This observation is true for not only mononuclear but also for several dinuclear and polymeric complexes⁶⁸. There is a universal tendency for dioxomolybdenum(vi) complexes to adopt a *cis*-configuration with a strong disposition for octahedral structures^{69,70}, although appropriately rigid or sterically demanding ligands can enforce lower coordination numbers or non-octahedral coordination geometry on the Mo sphere⁷¹. In molybdoenzymes there is a strong evidence for the presence of an MoO_2^{2+} grouping^{27,72}. The infrared (or Raman) absorptions are by far the most characteristic feature, to identify the presence of the MoO_2^{2+} unit^{73,74}. Nmr (¹H and ¹³C) spectra are often useful in a complementary way in establishing the disposition of the remaining non-oxo ligands^{75,76} and in establishing the lability or fluxionality of the coordinated ligands^{75,77}.

The method of choice for the preparation of many dioxomolybdenum(vi) complexes is involving the use of $\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2$, which is easily prepared from MoO_4^{2-} and acetylacetonone (acacH) by adjusting the pH^{78,79}. The reaction of equation (2) is typical and proceeds readily in THF⁸⁰.

The incoming ligand is generally ionised by addition of a base. In the absence of base, the free acacH (b.p. 139°) formed can be readily distilled under partial vacuum from the reaction solution alongwith the solvent. The acetylacetonate group in $\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2$ behaves as an innocent ligand and could be either partly or totally replaced by other ligands.

Although a large number of Schiff base complexes of lighter transition elements are known, relatively less were reported on the complexes with molybdenum⁸¹. In recent years, several *cis*-dioxomolybdenum(vi) complexes of several bi-, tri- and tetradentate Schiff base ligands are reported to stimulate many characteristic properties of the active sites of molybdoenzymes. Thus, the bidentate ligands (H₂L) form MoO_2L_2 complexes^{82,83}, while the tetradentate ligands (H₂L'') form $\text{MoO}_2\text{L}''$ complexes^{84,85}. With tridentate ligands (H₂L'), complexes are formed^{86,87} which are coordinatively unsaturated and can accept a monodentate donor ligand (D) forming complexes of the type $[\text{MoO}_2\text{L}'(\text{D})]$. The work reported in this paper is concerned with the complexes of dioxomolybdenum(vi) with multidentate Schiff bases. Using $\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2$ as the source for MoO_2^{2+} , tri-, tetra-, penta- and hexadentate Schiff base complexes were obtained. Although it is possible to synthesise either mono- or binuclear complexes containing the MoO_2^{2+} core or binuclear complexes containing the Mo_2O_5 or Mo_2O_3 core unit, in all cases either mono- or binuclear complexes with MoO_2^{2+} core were obtained. Indeed, with the tridentate Schiff base ligands only mononuclear complexes were formed, whereas with the tetra-, penta- and hexadentate ligands binuclear complexes were formed where these ligands bridge the two MoO_2^{2+} core units.

$\text{MoO}_2\text{L}'(\text{D})$ complexes

Using dibasic, tridentate ligands (H₂SAE, H₂SAP, H₂SAPT) (H₂L') with $\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2$ in presence of imidazole base, the six-coordinated $[\text{MoO}_2\text{L}'(\text{D})]$ (D = imidazole or substituted imidazole) complexes were obtained. These complexes are of interest as it is known that several mixed-ligand complexes play an important role in many naturally occurring biological processes⁸⁸. The reaction of a dibasic, tridentate ligand with MoO_2^{2+} renders the sixth coordination site vacant in the electrically neutral molybdenum(vi) complex and this vacant site may be envisaged as providing a suitable bonding site for the substrates during a catalytic cycle. The tridentate ligands employed are synthesised by the condensation of salicylal-

dehyde with 2-amino-1-ethanol (H_2SAE)⁸⁹, 2-aminophenol (H_2SAP)⁸⁶ and 2-aminothiophenol (H_2SAPT)^{90,91}. These ligands react with $\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2$ in presence of imidazole base leading to the removal of both the acetylacetonate groups forming the complex $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{SB})(\text{D})]$, ($\text{H}_2\text{SB} = \text{H}_2\text{SAE}, \text{H}_2\text{SAP}, \text{H}_2\text{SAPT}$)

D = imidazole base

These complexes are yellow to orange-red in colour, diamagnetic and non-electrolytic in nature. Invariably always the $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ vibrations of the free Schiff bases observed⁸⁹ around 1630 cm^{-1} is shifted to lower frequencies and appear as a split band in the region close to 1600 cm^{-1} suggesting the coordination as an anionic ligand through the O and N atoms^{92,93}. The aromatic

Fig. 5. Infrared absorption bands due to the cis-MoO_2^{2+} and $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAP})]$ ($\text{SAP} = o$ -aminophenol salicylideneimine) complex.

$\nu_{\text{C}-\text{O}}$ vibrations of the ligand in complexes appear at $1540-1550 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region in all complexes and the aliphatic $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{O}}$ for $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAE})(\text{D})]$ complexes appear around $\sim 1040 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region⁹⁴. The broad hydrogen-bonded OH stretch near 2700 cm^{-1} of the free ligand is absent in the complexes, suggesting coordination of the ligands as deprotonated, dianionic ligand. The formation of Mo-O bonds with the Schiff base results in the appearance of few medium to strong bands in the $550-650 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region⁹⁶ and formation of Mo-N bonds with the Schiff base and imidazole results in the appearance of additional bands in the $520-600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region⁹⁵. The ir bands due to

TABLE 3—PROMINENT IR BANDS (cm⁻¹) FOR SOME SELECTED [MoO₂(SB)(D)] COMPLEXES

Compd.*	SB vibrations			MoO ₂ ²⁺ vibrations
	VC=N	VC-O	VMo-O	VMo=O
[MoO ₂ (SAE)(Im)]	1 619 1 599	1 550 1 040	560	937, 922, 912
[MoO ₂ (SAE)(1-EtIm)]	1 617 1 599	1 555 1 035	580	936, 919, 904
[MoO ₂ (SAE)(1-BuIm)]	1 614 1 600	1 548 1 038	562	928, 912, 898
[MoO ₂ (SAE)(1-Allm)]	1 600 1 594	1 552 1 036	620	938, 928, 917
[MoO ₂ (SAP)(Im)]	1 612 1 605	1 555	560	920, 905
[MoO ₂ (SAP)(1-EtIm)]	1 616 1 605	1 530	562	928, 900
[MoO ₂ (SAP)(1-ViIm)]	1 615 1 600	1 550	560	922, 900
[MoO ₂ (SAP)(1-Allm)]	1 615 1 605	1 555	560	928, 905
[MoO ₂ (SAPT)(Im)]	1 580	1 540	580	940, 900
[MoO ₂ (SAPT)(1-EtIm)]	1 585	1 538	560	930, 900
[MoO ₂ (SAPT)(1-ViIm)]	1 575	1 536	620	945, 920
[MoO ₂ (SAPT)(1-Allm)]	1 580	1 540	590	940, 910

*H₂SAE = ethanolamine salicylideneimine; H₂SAP = 2-amino phenol salicylideneimine, H₂SAPT = 2-aminothiophenol salicylideneimine.

the imidazole derivatives occur in almost identical positions and can be easily assigned⁹⁷. All the complexes show two or three ir bands in the region 890–938 cm⁻¹ due to the *cis*-MoO₂²⁺ group^{73,86}. The *trans*-MoO₂²⁺ configuration would have resulted in a single $\nu_{\text{Mo=O}}$ band.

The ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra of the complexes also show the coordination of the Schiff base ligands and the imidazole ligands. The ¹H and ¹³C nmr chemical shifts for [MoO₂(SAE)(D)] complexes measured in acetone-d₆ medium are presented in Table 4. In the pmr spectra, the aldiminic proton (–N=CH–) of the ligand⁹⁸ appearing as one-proton singlet at δ 8.19 experiences a somewhat downfield shift to δ 8.67 in the complexes. The aromatic protons are observed as a multiplet centred at about δ 7.5 and the methylene signals of the ligand backbone are seen as two sets of triplets at δ 3.89 and 4.51 in the complexes. The proton signals at δ 7.84, 7.08 and 7.07 are assigned to the H-2, H-4 and H-5 of the imidazole group⁹⁹ with the signals for the substituents assigned at appropriate positions. Similarly, the ¹³C nmr spectra of the com-

TABLE 4—¹H AND ¹³C NMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS OF [MoO₂(SAE)(D)] COMPLEXES IN (CD₃)₂CO*

Compd.	SAE Protons				Imidazole protons			R
	–N=CH	–C ₆ H ₅	–N–CH ₂	–N–CH ₂ –CH ₂	H-2	H-4	H-5	
[MoO ₂ (SAE)(Im)]	8.67	7.5	3.89	4.51	7.84	7.08	7.07	–
[MoO ₂ (SAE)(2-MeIm)]	8.64	7.4	3.81	4.47	–	7.06	7.07	2.4
[MoO ₂ (SAE)(1-EtIm)]	8.65	7.3	3.86	4.49	7.83	7.08	7.06	1.3 4.0
[MoO ₂ (SAE)(1-ViIm)]	8.62	7.5	3.88	4.45	7.84	7.07	7.06	5.14 5.46 6.95
[MoO ₂ (SAE)(1-Allm)]	8.66	7.4	3.87	4.48	7.82	7.08	7.07	4.05 5.46 5.30
Compd.	SAE carbons				Imidazole carbons			R
	–N=CH	–C ₆ H ₅	–N–CH ₂	–N–CH ₂ –CH ₂	C-2	C-4	C-5	
[MoO ₂ (SAE)(Im)]	209.9	164.9– 119.8	72.66	61.66	135.7	120.7	119.8	–
[MoO ₂ (SAE)(1-EtIm)]	209.5	164.5– 119.6	72.59	61.58	135.5	119.9	119.8	15.82 44.62
[MoO ₂ (SAE)(1-ViIm)]	209.7	164.6– 119.4	72.61	61.60	135.3	120.1	119.9	105.42 130.84
[MoO ₂ (SAE)(1-Allm)]	209.3	164.1– 119.2	72.58	61.59	135.6	120.6	119.7	49.98 118.21 133.51

*¹H chemical shifts (ppm) with TMS as internal standard and ¹³C chemical shifts (ppm) relative to internal (CD₃)₂CO resonating at 29.2 ppm downfield to TMS.

plexes reveal the coordination of the ligand to the MoO_2^{2+} core. The aldiminic carbon appears at 209.9 ppm with the aromatic carbon signals at 164.9, 163.6, 135.3, 134.7, 122.1 and 119.8 ppm. The methylene carbons of ligand skeleton appear at 61.6 and 72.6 ppm. The carbons at positions 2, 4 and 5 of the imidazole ring are clearly seen at 135.7, 120.7 and 119.8 ppm, respectively. Similar observations were made for $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAP})(\text{D})]$ and $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAPT})(\text{D})]$ complexes.

The complexes do not ionise under the conditions of the mass spectrometer and no molecular ion peak of the complexes is obtained nor any metallated fragmentation product is observed, rendering no assistance in providing further information. The electrochemical measurements in acetonitrile for $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAE})(\text{D})]$ complexes and for $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAPT})(\text{D})]$ complexes in DMF, provide the values for cathodic reduction potentials. In cyclic voltammetry, the complexes do not show any observable oxidation wave upon the reverse anodic scan of the cyclic voltammogram and thus exhibit irreversible redox behaviour¹⁰⁰. Indeed, several *cis*-dioxomolybdenum(vi) complexes¹⁰¹ have generally shown irreversible or quasi-reversible behaviour. These cathodic reduction potentials (E_{pc}) for $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAE})(\text{D})]$ complexes in CH_3CN medium are all obtained in a typically narrow range of -1.1 to -1.2 V vs Ag/AgCl. The cyclic voltammogram for a typical complex $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAE})(1\text{-EtIm})]$ in CH_3CN is shown in Fig. 6 as an example for what is observed for these complexes. The corresponding values for $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAPT})(\text{D})]$

Fig. 6 Cyclic voltammogram of $([\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAE})(1\text{-EtIm})]$ (H_2SAE = ethanolamine salicylideneimine, EtIm = ethyl imidazole) in acetonitrile

complexes in DMF is in the range of -1.11 to -1.18 V vs Ag/AgCl^{66,102}. The parent $\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAPT})$ complex in DMF also undergoes reduction in this potential range and the similarity in the results of electrochemical measurements for the parent $\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAPT})$ complex and the imidazole derivative $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAPT})(\text{D})]$ suggests that the monodentate imidazole ligands are rather easily replaced by the strongly coordinating solvent molecules (DMF) in agreement with earlier results on similar types of complexes¹⁰³. The ligands do not exhibit any redox activity in the potential range where the molybdenum reductions are observed. These measurements in acetonitrile for $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAP})(\text{D})]$, however, show only weak responses indicating that the metal centre is not easily reducible in these¹⁰⁴ cases. The thermogravimetric analysis measurements clearly show that the complexes $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{SB})(\text{D})]$ ($\text{SB} = \text{H}_2\text{SAE}$, H_2SAP , H_2SAPT)^{94,102,104} decompose in a clearly well-defined endothermic step in the temperature range 150–180°, where the mass-loss corresponds to the loss of imidazole ligands. This is also an evidence in favour of the relative labile binding of the imidazole ligands in the solid state. On further heating beyond this stage, total loss of organic matter occurs in steps ultimately forming MoO_3 or Mo_3O_8 as the final product at 500–550°.

Bridged binuclear $[(\text{acac})\text{MoO}_2(\text{L-L})\text{O}_2\text{Mo}(\text{acac})]$ complexes

As already discussed, $\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2$ is a convenient source for MoO_2^{2+} ions. The reaction of $\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2$ in suitable solvents, with the multidentate Schiff bases obtained by the condensation of biacetylmonoxime with ethylenediamine (H_2DMPD), diethylene triamine (H_2DMDT) and triethylenetetramine (H_2DMTT) (10), yields binu-

clear, mixed-ligand, six-coordinated, *cis*-dioxomolybdenum(vi) complexes, [(*acac*)MoO₂(L-L)O₂Mo(*acac*)] (18) by the partial displacement of the acetylacetonate group from the parent MoO₂(*acac*)₂ complex. The polydentate oxime-based Schiff base ligands (18) may coordinate to a single metal centre^{105,106} or to two metal centres^{60,64,107}. These ligands behave as doubly-deprotonated tetradentate ligands and bridge the two MoO₂(*acac*)⁺ centres, on reaction with MoO₂(*acac*)₂. That only one *acac* group is displaced from each Mo(*acac*)₂ is confirmed by the isolation of Cu(*acac*)₂ quantitatively after the reaction with the H₂L ligands and formation of complexes (18). Similar partial displacement of *acac* groups from MoO₂(*acac*)₂¹⁰⁸, VO(*acac*)₂¹⁰⁹ and Zr(*acac*)₄¹¹⁰ have been observed.

All the complexes, [(*acac*)MoO₂(L-L)O₂Mo(*acac*)], exhibit ir spectrum which manifests itself in the form of an intense two-band pattern^{73,74} corresponding to the symmetric and antisymmetric Mo=O stretching vibrations in the 880–920 cm⁻¹ region. The ν_{C=N} band of the Schiff bases appear at 1580–1620 cm⁻¹ and the ν_{N-O} at 1140–1150 cm⁻¹ suggests the N-coordination of the oxime group^{60,96}. The ν_{N-O} and δ_{N-O} bands appear at 1080 and 820 cm⁻¹ respectively. The ν_{C=O} band of the coordinated *acac* group⁶³ is seen at 1580 cm⁻¹ and the methine C–H bending vibrations is observed as a weak band at 1190 cm⁻¹. The formation of Mo–O bonds with *acac* groups and Mo–N bonds of the Schiff bases results in the observance of few medium to strong stretch-

ing frequencies in the 550–650 cm⁻¹ region, which are absent in the free ligands. That one or two secondary amine (NH) functions remain uncoordinated in the complexes with the pentadentate H₂DMDT and the hexadentate H₂DMTT ligand is seen from the appearance of ν_{NH} at *ca* 3150 cm⁻¹, which is further substantiated by ¹H nmr spectra.

The PMR and CMR spectra establish in a complementary way the disposition of the non-oxo ligands in the complexes⁶³. The two sharp signals in the δ 1.7–2.0 ppm region in the PMR spectra correspond to the two non-equivalent CH₃ groups in the Schiff base ligands. The CH₂–CH₂ signals are seen at δ 3.3–3.9. In the CMR spectra, the two ¹³C signals due to the non-equivalent CH₃ groups are seen at 8.6 and 12.9–13.4 ppm in the ligands shifting somewhat downfield in complexes to *ca* 10.4 and 18.4 ppm respectively. The CH₂–CH₂ carbons resonating at 48.9–52.32 ppm for free ligands shift to 42.5–48.9 ppm in the complexes. The carbons (C^c and C^d) in the diacetylmonoxime skeleton resonate at 156.48 and 164.1–165.1 ppm respectively, for free ligands shifting only slightly downfield in the complexes. Additional proton signals at *ca* 2.0 and 5.4 ppm and carbon signals at 30.6, 98.7 and 196.7 ppm in the PMR and CMR spectrum respectively, demonstrate the unequivocal presence of coordinated acetylacetonate group in all the complexes⁶³. The NH proton signals in pentadentate H₂DMDT and the hexadentate H₂DMTT ligands

TABLE 5-¹H NMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS (PPM) FOR [(*acac*)MoO₂(L-L)O₂Mo(*acac*)] COMPLEXES IN (CD₃)₂SO*

Compd	Schiff base protons				acac protons	
	CH ₃ ^a	CH ₃ ^b	CH ₂ -CH ₂	NH	CH ₃	CH
H ₂ DMED	1.88	2.04	3.75			
[Mo ₂ O ₄ (<i>acac</i>) ₂ (DMED)]	1.78	1.91	3.49		2.1	5.4
H ₂ DMDT	1.72	1.92	3.43	8.38		
			3.53			
[Mo ₂ O ₄ (<i>acac</i>) ₂ (DMDT)]	1.86	1.93	3.58	10.55	2.08	5.2
			3.80			
H ₂ DMTT	1.90	1.98	3.27	8.31		
			3.36			
			3.42			
[Mo ₂ O ₄ (<i>acac</i>) ₂ (DMTT)]	1.86	1.93	3.49	10.52	2.14	5.0
			3.64			
			3.93			

*TMS as internal standard.

TABLE 6— ^{13}C NMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS FOR $[(\text{acac})\text{MoO}_2(\text{L-L})\text{O}_2\text{Mo}(\text{acac})]$ COMPLEXES IN $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{SO}^*$

Compd.	Schiff base carbons					acac carbons		
	CH_3^a	CH_3^b	$\text{CH}_2\text{-CH}_2$	C^c	C^d	CH_3	CH	CO
H_2DMED	8.64	12.96	52.32	156.48	165.12			
$[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4(\text{acac})_2(\text{DMED})]$	10.4	18.22	48.51	164.30	168.54	30.6	98.7	196.7
H_2DMDT	8.64	12.96	49.92	156.48	164.64			
			51.36					
$[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4(\text{acac})_2(\text{DMDT})]$	10.07	18.41	46.52	162.70	166.46	28.9	95.9	194.1
			47.65					
H_2DMTT	8.64	13.44	48.96	156.48	164.16			
			49.92					
			51.84					
$[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4(\text{acac})_2(\text{DMTT})]$	10.25	18.42	42.59	162.81	167.27	28.6	95.5	193.7
			45.81					
			48.92					

*All values in ppm relative to internal DMSO-d_6 resonating as a heptet centred at 39.6 ppm downfield to TMS.

appear at 8.3 ppm and shift to 10.5 ppm in the complexes, providing proof for the presence of free NH groups. The relevant ^1H and ^{13}C nmr data are presented in Tables 5 and 6 respectively, and the ^{13}C nmr of a typical complex is presented in Fig. 7. The thermal analysis meas-

Fig. 7. ^{13}C nmr spectrum of $[(\text{acac})(\text{MoO}_2(\text{DMTT})\text{O}_2\text{Mo}(\text{acac}))]$ (H_2DMTT = 3,14-dimethyl-4,7,10,13-tetraazahexadeca-3,13-diene-2,15-dione dioxime; H_2acac = acetylacetonate) complex in DMSO-d_6 .

urements clearly reveal the decomposition patterns of the complexes with increasing temperatures forming MoO_3 as the stable end product around $550\text{--}650^\circ\text{C}$.

The results discussed here establish the formation of binuclear, ligand-bridged, mixed-ligand, six-coordinated dioxomolybdenum complexes where each molybdenum(vi) is surrounded by two oxo ligands, one bidentate acac group and two N-donor atoms (oxime N and imine N) of the Schiff bases. The potential pentadentate H_2DMDT and the hexadentate H_2DMTT ligands essentially func-

tion as bridging tetradentate ligands (like the tetradentate H_2DMED or H_2DMPD) with one or two secondary amine groups (NH) remaining uncoordinated in the complexes. Similar observations have been made from this laboratory earlier for cobalt(III)⁶⁰, thorium(IV)⁶², uranium(VI)⁶² and vanadium(V)⁵⁹ complexes.

Prospects

The chemistry of vanadium and molybdenum is of topical interest as both of them have a large number of accessible oxidation states offering a wide variety of compounds with diverse coordination numbers and stereochemistries and as both of them are biologically very significant. Some similarities between vanadate and phosphate ions explain the biological activity of vanadium in the 5+ oxidation state. The most remarkable example is the striking inhibition of the Na^+ pump (Na^+ , K^+ -ATPase). Vanadium complexes of hydrazine derivatives of a nitrogen heterocycle are used in treatment of arteriosclerosis and to lower blood pressure¹¹¹ and some peroxovanadium complexes have potential insulin-like activity and are proposed as orally active alternatives to insulin¹⁷. Since the biological role of molybdenum was recognised¹¹², an increasing volume of evidence has accumulated to show that molybdenum is essential for a significant number of biological processes. Molybdenum is required both for nitrogen fixation and nitrate reduction and

its participation in some animal hydroxylase enzyme and several fungal and bacterial enzymes is firmly established. The molybdoenzymes are all reasonably large proteins, the functions of which involve the molybdenum centres undergoing redox reactions in concert with other redox active constituents. The great developments in electrochemical techniques will obviously play a great role in the study of redox processes of both vanadium and molybdenum which occur in large numbers of oxidation states. Multinuclear nmr spectrometers will allow extensive uses of ^{51}V and ^{95}Mo resonances as a routine technique in the characterisation of complexes. Other future developments will include the study of polynuclear complexes (both homo- and heteronuclear) and mixed valence complexes and it can be anticipated that these areas will soon become important areas of their chemistry, although isolation of compounds of such complex structures is again symptomatic of the difficulties that may be encountered for these metal ions. The prospects for chemistry of vanadium and molybdenum are truly immense and vast, and an interesting future with rich dividends is in store.

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References

1. S. A. MILLER, T. W. HAMBLEY and J. C. TAYLOR, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1984, **37**, 761.
2. M. G. B. DREW, P. C. H. MITCHELL and C. E. SCOTT, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1984, **82**, 63.
3. H. KNEIFEL and E. BAYER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **108**, 3075.
4. E. BAYER, E. KOCH and G. ANDEREGG, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1987, **26**, 544.
5. G. ANDEREGG, E. KOCH and E. BAYER, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1987, **127**, 183.
6. K. KUSHTIN and I. G. MACARA, *Comments Inorg. Chem.*, 1982, **1**, 1.
7. E. BAYER and H. KNEIFEL, *Z. Naturforsch., Teil B*, 1972, **27**, 207.
8. H. KNEIFEL and E. BAYER, *Angew. Chem.*, 1973, **85**, 542.
9. L. C. CANTLEY, JR., L. G. CANTLEY and L. J. JOSEPHSON, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1978, **253**, 7361.
10. T. ALBER, W. A. GILBERT, D. R. PONZI and G. A. PETSKO, *Ciba Found. Symp.*, 1983, **93**, 4.
11. A. WLODAWER, M. MILLER and L. SJOLIN, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA*, 1983, **80**, 3628.
12. G. L. CURRAN and R. E. BURCH, *Proc. Univ. Mo. Annu. Conf. Trace Subst. Environ. Health, Ist.*, 1967, 96.
13. C. DJORDJEVIC and G. L. WAMPLER, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 1985, **25**, 51.
14. D. REHDER, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1991, **30**, 148.
15. A. BUTLER and C. J. CARRANO, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1991, **109**, 61.
16. R. WEVER and K. KUSTIN, *Adv. Inorg. Chem.*, 1990, **35**, 81.
17. S. BORMAN, *Chem. Engg. News*, 1994, Feb. 21, p. 35.
18. B. C. GATES, J. R. KATZER and G. C. A. SCHUIT, "Chemistry of Catalytic Processes", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1979.
19. M. L. H. GREEN in "Proceedings of the Third International Conference on the Chemistry and Uses of Molybdenum", eds. H. E. BARRY and P. C. H. MITCHELL, Climax Molybdenum Company, Ann Arbor, 1979, p. 14.
20. J. TOPICH and J. L. LYON, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1984, **23**, 3202.
21. E. I. STIEFEL, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1977, **22**, 1.
22. J. LEVY, J. J. R. CAMPBELL and T. H. BLACKBURN, "Introductory Microbiology", Wiley, New York, 1973.
23. E. J. HEWITT, *Biol. Rev.*, 1959, **34**, 333.
24. F. R. N. GURD and D. S. GOODMAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 670.
25. "Molybdenum Chemistry of Biological Significance", eds.

- W. E. NEWTON and S. OTSUKA, Plenum, London, 1980.
26. R. HILLE and V. MASSEY in "Molybdenum Enzymes", ed. T. G. SPIRO, Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1985.
 27. S. J. N. BURGMAYER and E. I. STIEFEL, *J. Chem. Educat.*, 1985, **62**, 943.
 28. L. V. BOAS and J. C. PESSOA in "Comprehensive Coordination Chemistry", eds. G. WILKINSON, R. D. GILLARD and J. A. McCLEVERTY, Pergamon, Oxford, 1987, Vol. 3, p. 454.
 29. J. SELBIN, *Chem. Rev.*, 1965, **65**, 153.
 30. C. J. BALLHAUSEN and H. B. GRAY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **1**, 111.
 31. L. G. VANQUICKENBORNE and S. P. McGLYNN, *Theor. Chim. Acta*, 1968, **9**, 390.
 32. D. COLLISON, B. GAHAN, C. D. GARNER and F. E. MABBS, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1980, 667.
 33. H. JOHANSEN and K. TANAKA, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1985, **116**, 155.
 34. F. E. DICKSON, C. J. KUNESH, E. L. MCGINIS and L. PETRAKIS, *Anal. Chem.*, 1972, **44**, 978.
 35. R. J. H. CLARK, "The Chemistry of Titanium and Vanadium". Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968.
 36. R. A. ROWE and M. M. JONES, *Inorg. Synth.*, 1957, **5**, 114.
 37. R. P. DODGE, D. H. TEMPLETON and A. ZALKIN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1961, **35**, 55.
 38. P. K. HON, R. L. BELFORD and C. E. PFLUGER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1965, **43**, 3111.
 39. D. A. JOHNSON and A. B. WAUGH, *Polyhedron*, 1983, **2**, 1323.
 40. A. SERIANZ, J. R. SHELTON, F. L. URBACH, R. C. DUNBAR and R. F. KOPCZEWSKI, *J. Chem. Educat.*, 1976, **53**, 394.
 41. M. NAWI and T. L. RIECHEL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1981, **20**, 1974.
 42. R. D. BEREMAN and D. NALEWAJEK, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1978, **40**, 1313.
 43. D. BRUINS and D. L. WEAVER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, **9**, 130.
 44. P. K. NATH and K. C. DASH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, **25**, 968.
 45. R. L. DUTTA and G. P. SENGUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 919.
 46. A. P. GINSBERG, E. KOUBEK and H. J. WILLIAMS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 1656.
 47. B. BLEANY and K. D. BOWERS, *Proc. R. Soc. London, Ser. A*, 1952, **214**, 1451.
 48. A. SYAMAL and L. J. THERIOT, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1973, **2**, 193.
 49. A. SYAMAL and K. S. KALE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1977, **15**, 431; 1980, **19**, 486.
 50. P. K. NATH, N. C. MISHRA, V. CHAKRAVORTTY and K. C. DASH, *Z. Naturforsch., Teil B*, 1986, **41**, 1443.
 51. D. K. RASTOGI, S. K. SAHNI, V. B. RANA, K. DUA and S. K. DUA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1979, **41**, 21.
 52. V. V. ZELENTSOV, *Dokl. Akad. Nauk. SSSR*, 1961, **139**, 1110 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1962, **56**, 1442).
 53. B. A. GOODMAN and J. B. RAYNER *Adv. Inorg. Chem. Radiochem.*, 1970, **3**, 135.
 54. R. H. DUNHILL and T. D. SMITH, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1968, 2189.
 55. R. E. TAPSCOTT and R. L. BELFORD, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 735.
 56. K. C. DASH and H. N. MOHANTA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1978, **40**, 499.
 57. P. K. NATH, N. C. MISRA, V. CHAKRAVORTTY and K. C. DASH, *Polyhedron*, 1987, **6**, 455.
 58. R. N. MOHANTY, V. CHAKRAVORTTY and K. C. DASH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1991, **30**, 454.
 59. R. N. MOHANTY, V. CHAKRAVORTTY and K. C. DASH, Unpublished results.
 60. M. MOHAPATRA, V. CHAKRAVORTTY and K. C. DASH, *Polyhedron*, 1989, **8**, 1509.
 61. M. MOHAPATRA and K. C. DASH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1990, **29**, 342.
 62. S. SINGH, V. CHAKRAVORTTY and K. C. DASH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1989, **28**, 255; 1990, **29**, 397.
 63. R. N. MOHANTY and K. C. DASH, *Polyhedron*, 1990, **9**, 1011.
 64. K. C. DASH, B. FÖLKESSON, R. LARSSON and M. MOHAPATRA, *J. Electron Spectrosc. Related Phenomena*, 1989, **43**, 343.
 65. A. G. SYKES in "Comprehensive Coordination Chemistry", eds. G. WILKINSON, R. D. GILLARD and J. A. McCLEVERTY, Pergamon, Oxford, 1987, Vol. 3, p. 1229.
 66. K. C. DASH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **69**, 501.
 67. "Proceedings of the Climax International Conference on the Chemistry and Uses of Molybdenum", 1973 (Reading), 1970 (Oxford), 1979 (Ann Arbor) and 1982 (Colorado); "Proceedings of the Fifth Conference" held at Newcastle in 1985 published in *Polyhedron*, 1986, **5**, 1.
 68. J. M. BERG and R. H. HOLM, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **106**, 3035.
 69. J. M. BERG and K. O. HODGSON, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1980, **19**, 2180.
 70. J. M. BERG, D. J. SPIRA, K. WO, B. MCCORD, R. LYE, M. S. CO, J. BELMONT, C. BARNES, K. KOSYDAR, S. RAYBUCK, K. O. HODGSON, A. E. BRUCE, J. L. CORBIN and E. I. STIEFEL, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1984, **90**, 35.
 71. J. M. BERG and R. H. HOLM, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **107**, 917.
 72. S. P. CRAMER in "Advances in Inorganic and Bioinorganic Mechanisms", ed. A. G. SYKES, Academic, New York, 1983, Vol. 2, p. 259.
 73. W. E. NEWTON and J. W. McDONALD, *J. Less-Common Met.*, 1977, **54**, 51.
 74. L. WILLIS, T. LOEHR, A. E. BRUCE, K. MILLER and E.

- I. STIEFEL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1986, **25**, 4289.
75. J. K. HOWIE, P. BOSSERMAN and D. T. SAWYER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1980, **19**, 2293.
76. N. UEYAMA, K. KAMABUCHI and A. NAKAMURA, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1985, 635.
77. T. J. PINNAVAIA and W. R. CLEMENTS, *Inorg. Nucl. Chem. Lett.*, 1971, **7**, 1127.
78. H. GEHRKE, JR and J. VEAL, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1969, **3-4**, 623.
79. M. M. JONES, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 3188.
80. D. SELLMAN and L. ZAPI, *Z. Naturforsch, Teil B*, 1985, **40**, 368.
81. R. H. HOLM, G. W. EVERETT, JR. and A. CHAKRAVORTTY, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **7**, 83.
82. C. D. GARNER, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1981, **37**, 117.
83. S. GHOSH and S. PUROHIT, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, **26**, 131.
84. K. YAMANOUCHI and S. YAMADA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1974, **9**, 161.
85. D. D. AGARWAL and S. SRIVASTAVA, *Polyhedron*, 1988, **7**, 2569.
86. O. A. RAJAN and A. CHAKRAVORTY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1981, **20**, 660.
87. J. TOPICH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1981, **20**, 3704.
88. "Metal Ions in Biological Systems", ed. H. SIGEL, Marcel Dekker, New York, 1973, Vol. 2, p. 101.
89. J. TOPICH and J. T. LYONS, III, *Polyhedron*, 1984, **3**, 55.
90. E. C. ALYEA, A. MALEK and P. H. MERRELL, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1974, **4**, 55.
91. Y. MUTO, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1960, **33**, 1242.
92. J. R. DILWORTH, C. A. MCAULIFFE and B. J. SAYLE, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1977, 849.
93. K. YAMANOUCHI and S. YAMADA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1975, **12**, 9.
94. R. N. MOHANTY, V. CHAKRAVORTTY and K. C. DASH, *Polyhedron*, 1991, **10**, 33.
95. C. KNOBLER, B. R. PENFOLD, W. T. ROBINSON, C. J. WILKINS and S. H. YONG, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1980, 248.
96. K. BURGER, I. RUFF and F. RUFF, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, **27**, 109.
97. K. C. DASH and P. PUJARI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 2061.
98. E. C. ALYEA and A. MALEK, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1975, **53**, 939.
99. G. ROYCHOUDHURY and K. C. DASH, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 1980, **68**, 319.
100. R. D. TAYLOR, J. P. STREET, M. MINELLI and J. T. SPENCE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1978, **17**, 3207.
101. C. A. CLIFF, G. D. FALLON, B. M. GATEHOUSE, K. S. MURRAY and P. J. NEWMAN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1980, **19**, 773.
102. R. N. MOHANTY, V. CHAKRAVORTTY and K. C. DASH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1991, **30**, 457.
103. S. PUROHIT, A. P. KOLEY, L. S. PRASAD, P. T. MONOHARAN and S. GHOSH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1989, **28**, 3735.
104. P. K. NATH and K. C. DASH, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1985, **10**, 262.
105. A. V. ABLOV, N. I. BELICHUK and V. N. KAFTANAT, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, **17**, 392.
106. J. G. MOHANTY, R. P. SINGH and A. CHAKRAVORTTY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1975, **18**, 1207.
107. N. I. BELICHUK, A. V. ABLOV and V. N. KAFTANAT, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1973, **18**, 207.
108. S. LEE, C. FLORIANI, A. CHIESI-VILLA and C. GUASTINI, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1989, 145.
109. R. N. HIDER and C. J. WILKINS, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1984, 495.
110. P. K. MISHRA, V. CHAKRAVORTTY and K. C. DASH, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1991, **16**, 73.
111. Ciba Ltd., Belg. Pat. 6 13 432/1962 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1963, **58**, 11374).
112. H. BORTELS, *Arch. Mikrobiol.*, 1930, **1**, 33.